

pH-Metric and Thermodynamic Studies of Metal-Benzamidothiosemicarbazide Interaction

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Manuscript received 28 January 1982, accepted 28 January 1983

Formation of Pb(II) and Hg(II) complex with benzamidothiosemicarbazide has been realised below pH 8.3. pH-metric titrations show that protons are released and the anionic form of the benzamidothiosemicarbazide takes part in the formation of 1:2 metal-benzamidothiosemicarbazide complex. The stepwise stability constants were calculated at different temp. by Calvin and Melchior method and corrected by Bjerrum's method of successive approximation. The values of corrected overall stability constants ($\log K$) for Pb(II) complex are 6.70, 6.62, 6.52 and 6.45; and for Hg(II) complex are 12.75, 12.65, 12.58, and 12.49 at 25, 30, 35 and 40°, respectively. The thermodynamic parameters calculated at 25° are $\Delta G^\circ = -38.2269 \text{ k J mole}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\circ = -3.0635 \text{ k J mole}^{-1}$, and $\Delta S^\circ = 117.9 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$ for Pb(II) complex and $\Delta G^\circ = -72.7496 \text{ k J mole}^{-1}$, $\Delta H^\circ = -3.1114 \text{ k J mole}^{-1}$ and $\Delta S^\circ = 233.3 \text{ J K}^{-1} \text{ mole}^{-1}$ for Hg(II) complex. Reaction between metal and benzamidothiosemicarbazide proceeds spontaneously as ΔG° is negative, and the negative values of ΔH° suggests that these reactions are exothermic. Positive values of entropy shows formation of stable complexes.

WE had earlier reported^{1,2} the studies of Cu(II), Pb(II) and Hg(II) complexes with benzamidothiosemicarbazide. The results of our studies on the composition, stepwise stability constant and overall stability constant as well as thermodynamic parameters of benzamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) complex with Pb(II) and Hg(II) are reported here.

Experimental

Benamidothiosemicarbazide (BTSC) solution was prepared by dissolving weighed amount in 80:20 ethyl alcohol-water mixture. Fresh solution of BTSC was always used. Stock solutions of lead acetate and mercuric chloride were prepared by dissolving these salts (B. D. H., 'AR' grade) in CO₂-free double distilled water. The strength of these solutions was determined by usual methods. Elico pH-meter, with glass electrode and SCE was used for pH measurements. Standard solution of KOH was added to the reaction mixture from a micro burette (least count 0.05 ml). All pH measurements were performed at different temperatures, using Toshniwal thermostatic bath.

Results and Discussion

The pK value (8.1) of BTSC determined pH metrically was in agreement with the values obtained polarographically³. pH titrations performed with mixtures of metal and ligand, ligand and metal

separately against 0.1 M KOH showed lowering of pH, indicating liberation of protons as a result of complex formation. Further, maximum lowering of pH in case of 1:2 metal-BTSC mixture and the inflection corresponding to 2 moles of KOH:1 mole of metal indicated 1:2 metal-ligand ratio in the complex.

At different temperatures, the pH titration of BTSC alone and in presence of different concentrations of metal ions performed according to the method of Calvin and Melchior⁴ gave normal pH-metric curves when titrated against 0.1 M KOH. From these curves at various values of pH; different sets of \bar{n} values were determined and the corresponding concentrations of free ligand (A⁻) were calculated. The values of \bar{n} were plotted against the corresponding values of pA. Normal formation curves were obtained for both the metals at different temperatures. As a first approximation the values of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ and at $\bar{n}=1.5$ gave $\log K_1$ and $\log K_2$ respectively and summation of the two gave overall stability constant ($\log K$). These values are given in Tables 1 and 2.

These constants were further refined by Bjerrum's method⁵ of successive approximations. The value of spreading factor 'X' was calculated at different temperatures (Table 3) and the corrected values of formation functions (\bar{n}) for corresponding values of A⁻ were then plotted against pA. The final values of stepwise stability constants and overall stability constant are also tabulated in Tables 1 and 2.

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TABLE 1—VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR Pb-COMPLEX

Temp. °C	Experimental values			Corrected values		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K
25	3.70	3.00	6.70	3.85	2.85	6.70
30	3.68	2.94	6.62	3.88	2.79	6.62
35	3.64	2.88	6.52	3.80	2.72	6.52
40	3.60	2.85	6.45	3.76	2.69	6.45

Fig. 1, curve 1.

TABLE 2—VALUES OF STABILITY CONSTANTS FOR Hg-COMPLEX

Temp. °C	Experimental values			Corrected values		
	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K	log K ₁	log K ₂	log K
25	6.75	6.00	12.75	6.90	5.85	12.75
30	6.72	5.90	12.62	6.85	5.80	12.65
35	6.69	5.89	12.58	6.84	5.74	12.58
40	6.64	5.86	12.50	6.50	5.99	12.49

Fig. 1, curve 2.

TABLE 3—VALUES OF SPREADING FACTOR 'X' AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

Complex	Values of spreading factor			
	25°	30°	35°	40°
Pb(C ₈ H ₉ ON ₄ S) ₂	1.119	1.172	1.199	1.186
Hg(C ₈ H ₉ ON ₄ S) ₂	1.186	1.285	1.256	1.227

From the knowledge of overall stability constant, enthalpy change (ΔH°) using the relation $-\Delta H^\circ/2.303R = d(\log K)/d(1/T)$ (Fig. 1, curve 1 and 2), free energy change (ΔG°) using the relation $\Delta G^\circ = -RT \log K$ and entropy change (ΔS°) using the relation $\Delta S^\circ = \Delta H^\circ - \Delta G^\circ/T$, were calculated at 25° (Table 4).

It is clear from pH measurements that \bar{n} increases with the increase in pH showing thereby that it is the anionic form of the ligand which takes part in the reaction. Furthermore, reaction between metal salts and BTSC proceeds spontaneously as ΔG° is negative and the negative values of enthalpy suggest

Fig. 1

TABLE 4—THERMODYNAMIC PARAMETERS

Complex	ΔG° (kJ mole ⁻¹)	ΔH° (kJ mole ⁻¹)	ΔS° (JK ⁻¹ mole ⁻¹)
Pb(C ₈ H ₉ ON ₄ S) ₂	-38.2269	-3.0635	117.9
Hg(C ₈ H ₉ ON ₄ S) ₂	-72.7496	-3.1114	233.3

that these reactions are exothermic. Positive values of entropy shows formation of stable complexes.

References

1. M. N. ANSARI, M. C. JAIN and W. U. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 1023.
2. M. N. ANSARI, M. C. JAIN, R. D. KAUSHIK and W. U. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1982, **59**, 414.
3. M. N. ANSARI, M. C. JAIN and W. U. MALIK, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1980, **57**, 909.
4. M. CALVIN and N. C. MELCHIOR, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1948, **70**, 3270.
5. J. BJERRUM, "Metal Ammine Formation in Aqueous Solution", P. Haase and Son, Copenhagen, 1941.